

Deliverable 8.7: Intermediate version of training material on PTES

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Funded by EU TREASURE project

TREASURE

Demonstrating large pit thermal energy storages and improving their components, processes, and procedures for an accelerated realisation of 100% sustainable district heating networks in Europe.

PROJECT INTRODUCTION

Funded by
the European Union

TREASURE is

A 48-month-long research project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the topic **sustainable, secure and competitive energy supply** under Grant Agreement No. 101136095.

START

January 2024

END

December 2027

Thermal energy storages

- Introduction and principles

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$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\lambda}{\rho c_p} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2}$$

$\Delta \int_a^b \epsilon \Theta^{\sqrt{17}} + \Omega \int \delta e^{i\pi} =$
 $\infty = \{2.7182818284\}$
 $\chi^2 \Sigma !$

Academic background : Fluid dynamics and heat transfer

Research Fields and Interests:

- Energy storages, large scale heat storages, water pit heat storage, ground heat storages, phase change materials.
- Solar district heating systems, active solar heating systems for domestic hot water services and/or space heating, solar collectors, heat pumps, design and control of solar/electric heating systems.
- CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) calculation, Experimental Fluid Dynamics techniques such as PIV (Particle Image Velocimetry).

Teaching:

41465/11124 CFD on Buildings

41466/11127 Sustainable heating and cooling of buildings

41464/11117 Solar heating systems

47330 Energy storage and conversion

Lecture 10:

- Overview of heat storage technologies
- Latent heat storage and sensible heat storage
- Introduction to the assignment

Lecture 11:

- Design of water pit heat storage
- Design of hot water tank

Lecture 12:

- System integration of TES in the energy systems
- Economical analysis and optimization

Lecture 13:

- Thermal performance of water pit heat storages
- Simulation models of TES
- Summary of the four lectures on TES
- Course evaluation

Mentimeter survey on your background

- There are 3 ways to participate:

1:

<https://www.menti.com/al6v94o56cdh>

2:

<https://www.mentimeter.com/>

Code: 39732301

3: Scan the QR code

Welcome to the 'Thermal' world

- **08:15-08:50**
The importance of heat storage
Latent heat storage and sensible heat storage
- **08:50-9:00**
Break
- **9:00- 9:50**
System integration of heat storages and introduction of the heat storage assignment
- **9:50-12:00**
Exercise and assignment

Energy storages

Different energy storage technologies should work together

Thermal energy storage: efficiency will be higher for heating than for electricity

Energy storages

Pumped-storage hydropower station
Conghua, China

Lithium battery storage power station
Victoria, Australia

Seasonal pit heat storage
Dronninglund, Denmark

Mechanical Energy Storage

- Mature technology
- High efficiency
- Rapid response

Depends on Topography

Chemical Energy Storage

- High energy density
- High efficiency
- Rapid response

High cost & Poor safety

Thermal Energy Storage

- Large capacity
- High safety
- Low cost

Low energy density

“Solar + TES” is a promising technique for future energy supply.

Large share of heating demand

Status relating to energy use within EU

33%

of all energy in EU is used for **transport**

26%

of all energy in EU is used by **industry**

41%

of all energy in EU is used by **buildings**

2/3 of energy consumption in buildings is used for heating and cooling.

80% of energy consumption is used in small buildings < 1000 m²

The total energy consumption in Denmark: 194 TWh (2019)

Electricity	29 TWh	(15%)
Heat	82 TWh	(42%)
Transport & others	83 TWh	(43%)

Heat storage is the most efficiency and economically attractive energy storage for heating applications.

Sources:

1. <https://ourworldindata.org/energy/country/denmark>
2. Comprehensive Assessment 2020 Denmark, Energistyreslen
https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/default/files/dk_ca_2020_en.pdf

Why thermal energy storage?

The problem:

Higher share of wind, PV, solar heat, etc lead to two problems:

- 1. Mismatch between fluctuating nature of renewable energy and need for stable heat demand
- 2. Seasonal mismatch between solar and heating demand

Electricity market price Nord Pool

Energy storage is needed

The need for thermal energy storage

The mismatch between heating demand and production
 The need for heat storage

Hot water tank
Water pit heat storage

Phase change material
heat storage

Source: <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-819723-3.00006-8>

Sodium acetate trihydrate (SAT)

Source: Mehling et al. [1], source: ZAE Bayern

Applications of latent heat storage

In container

In walls/ floor

Microencapsulation

Macroencapsulation

Heat transport

Slurries (emulsion)

Fig.1 Micrograph of the emulsion.

Engineering aspects - heat transfer

Source: <https://doi.org/10.1533/9781782420965.2.285>

“Passive”
Heat transfer on the storage surface

Examples: Building structures, heating pads, functional clothing, etc.

“Active”
Heat transfer via surfaces with in the storage

Examples: Heating and cooling systems, ventilation systems, etc.

“Active”
Heat transfer by exchanging the storage medium

Examples: Slurries, transport of liquid PCM, etc.

Engineering aspects - heat transfer

Source: <https://doi.org/10.1533/9781782420965.2.285>

Low thermal power

Medium thermal power

High thermal power

High storage density

Medium storage density

Lower storage density

Usually used for temperature control

Usually for integration in hydraulic systems (liquid, air)

Enhancement of thermal heat transfer fluid capacity

Heat transfer:

- Low thermal conductivity (typically 0.15-0.7 W/ m K)
 - large heat exchange surface and/or conductivity enhancement needed
- Subcooling (unwanted in most applications)

Stability:

- Cyclic stability
 - Organic: sensitive temperature stability
 - Inorganic: phase separation
(separation of additives, crystal water, etc. in liquid state)

Interaction with other materials:

- Corrosion (expensive materials needed)
- Degradation

Temperature control of blood conserves

Heating pads

Cooling pads in armor vests

Fatty acids

Micro-encapsulated wax in automotive interior

Micro-encapsulated wax in bedding materials

Passive storage in buildings

- **Increase indoor thermal comfort** (air temperature peak reduction, decrease of daily temperature swing)
- **Enhancing the thermal capacity of the building**
- **Decrease the conditioning power needed** (reduction of the heating and cooling peak loads)
- Take advantage of **off-peak energy savings** (save money)
- Take advantage of **passive solar gain**
- Contribute for the **reduction of CO2 emissions for heating/cooling**

Soares, N., Costa, J. J., Gaspar, A. R., & Santos, P. (2013). Review of passive PCM latent heat thermal energy storage systems towards buildings' energy efficiency. *Energy and Buildings*, 59, 82–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2012.12.042>

Active storage – building ventilation

Free-cooling solutions for technical and server rooms → Utilization of ambient air, cooler than server room.

Macroencapsulated PCM plates
→ melting temperature ca. 20-25 °C.

In summer time, PCM can be used for **day/night storage**
(several hours of cooling capacity)

PCM solidification → night (charge)
PCM melting → day (discharge of cold)

Other system solutions:

- **Thermally active ceilings**
(airflow through perforated ceiling structures containing PCM)

<http://energy-cool.com/dk/produkter/air-storage/ec-air-peak-control/>

Example: Cooling system

- the slurry is pumped via heat exchanger to the heat pump
- High thermal power
- Reduced storage capacity
- Under development/ research

Fig.1 Micrograph of the emulsion.

Transport of heat

Was tested in research projects in Austria and in Bavaria:

Idea: Utilization of excess heat from industry in a production process of another industry (e.g. drying processes)

Material: Sodium Acetate Trihydrate
 → Salhydrate, melting temperature: 58 °C

- Minimum temperature for stable supercooling $\sim 80^{\circ}\text{C}$
 - In all parts of bulk
- Remains in liquid state below melting temperature
- Latent heat of fusion stored
 - Storage period could be months
- Latent heat released
 - When solidification is started

Sodium acetate trihydrate

Combination of short and long term heat storage

- Significant reduction of volume in comparison with water tanks
 - Loss-free storage in supercooled state
 - Multiple heat storage units
 - On-demand crystallization (utilization of heat of fusion)
- Sodium Acetate Trihydrate composite

G. Englmair, W. Kong, J. B. Berg, S. Furbo, and J. Fan, "Demonstration of a solar combi-system utilizing stable supercooling of sodium acetate trihydrate for heat storage", Applied Thermal Engineering, vol. 166, no. 114647, 2020.

Cylinder - $\Phi 0.4 \times 1.7$ m
 Steel - 166 kg
 Insulation - 30 mm

PCM - 137.8 kg
 Filled in 112 PCM tubes

Large heat transfer area: **16.2 m²**
Stirring Function: Form Bottom High-Top Low temperature distribution to increase the convection inside liquid PCM

At DTU

Dropping crystal Pipe:

A vertical pipe with a ball valve, SAT crystals could be inserted to trigger the solidification of the supercooled SAT.

Balancing pressure Pipe:

The inclined tube with an air filter prevents pressure changes in the PCM chamber as the PCM expands and contracts during heating and cooling.

Top volume over tubes:

The tops of the tubes were fixed to a steel plate and open to the volume above the plate.

Height of PCM: 1.52 m + 0.02 m

(in tube) (in top volume)

To prevent the lack of PCM inside tubes, 0.02 m more PCM is added.

It works

At DTU

10 min break

Steel tank

Water pit (PTES)

Borehole storage (BTES)

Aquifer storage

Steel tank 5500 m³

DT
◆◆◆

Construction of water pit heat storage

Surface area per volume

(Cylinder, Radius = Height)

1.2 → 0.1 → **Factor 12** on surface area/volume (heat loss/storage capacity)

Cost per equivalent m³

500 → 20 → **Factor 25** on costs/volume (cost/storage capacity)

Applications of different types of heat storages

- 4x TTES
- 3x PTES
- 2x BTES
- 1x ATES
- 1x TTES + BTES

Key parameters of heat storage

- Heat content/capacity
- Heat loss
- Heat recovery ratio/storage efficiency (short term, long term)
- Storage cycle/utilization frequency

Heat content of storage

General equation:

$$Q = \rho \cdot c \cdot \Delta T \cdot V$$

Q	Heat content of storage	(Joule)
ρ	Density of water	(kg/m ³)
c	Specific heat of water	(J/(kg· °C))
ΔT	Temperature difference of water	(K)
V	Water volume	(m ³)

temperature different, ΔT = Temperature of water store – reference temperature

For district heating, the reference T = the return T from the consumers (40°C)

Conversion of energy units:

$$1 \text{ kWh} = 3600 \cdot 1000 \text{ J} = 3.6 \cdot 10^6 \text{ J} = 3.6 \text{ MJ}$$

$$1 \text{ MWh} = 3.6 \text{ GJ}$$

Capacity of 100,000 m³ water TES:

$$4.667 \text{ GWh} = 4667 \text{ MWh}$$

Heat loss from a water pit heat storage

Heat loss = heat loss from the top lid sides + heat loss from the sides/bottom

Heat loss from a water pit heat storage during standby

Energy balance of the still water pit heat storage

Change of energy content = heat loss from the storage

Heat loss = heat loss from the top lid + bottom + sides

$$mC_p \frac{dT}{dt} = -UA_{top}(T - T_a) - UA_{soil}(T - T_{soil})$$

$$mC_p \frac{dT}{dt} = -[(UA_{top} + UA_{soil})T - UA_{top}T_a - UA_{soil}T_{soil}]$$

$$mC_p \frac{dT}{[(UA_{top} + UA_{soil})T - UA_{top}T_a - UA_{soil}T_{soil}]} = - dt$$

Integration of the differential equation:

$$m \int_{T_{start}}^{T_{end}} C_p \frac{dT}{[(UA_{top} + UA_{soil})T - UA_{top}T_a - UA_{soil}T_{soil}]} = - \int_0^{t_{end}} dt$$

$$\frac{mC_p}{(UA_{top} + UA_{soil})} \int_{T_{start}}^{T_{end}} \frac{dT}{[T - (UA_{top}T_a + UA_{soil}T_{soil}) / (UA_{top} + UA_{soil})]} = - \int_0^{t_{end}} dt$$

$$T_a^* = (UA_{top}T_a + UA_{soil}T_{soil}) / (UA_{top} + UA_{soil})$$

$$\frac{mC_p}{(UA_{top} + UA_{soil})} \ln \left(\frac{T_{end} - T_a^*}{T_{start} - T_a^*} \right) = - t_{end}$$

Heat loss from a water pit heat storage during standby (continued)

$$T_{end} = T_a^* + (T_{start} - T_a^*) \exp\left(\frac{-t_{end}(UA_{top} + UA_{soil})}{mC_p}\right)$$

C_p	Specific heat of water, J/kg/K
m	mass of the PTES, kg
t	time, s
t_{end}	duration, s
T	temperature of PTES, °C
T_a	ambient air temperature, °C
T_a^*	modified surrounding temperature, °C
T_{end}	temperature of PTES at the end of the period, °C
T_{start}	initial temperature of PTES, °C
T_{soil}	soil temperature around the PTES, °C
UA_{top}	heat loss coefficient from top cover of PTES to ambient, W/K
UA_{soil}	heat loss coefficient from the bottom and sides of PTES to soil, W/K

Heat recovery rate / storage efficiency

Definition of heat recovery rate/storage efficiency:

Heat taken from the store/Heat transferred to the store with in a given period

Condition: same energy content in the store

$$\text{Heat recovery rate} = \frac{\Sigma \text{Heat discharged}}{\Sigma \text{Heat charged}}$$

$$\text{Power} = \text{mass flow rate} * \text{specific heating} * (T_{\text{outlet}} - T_{\text{inlet}})$$

$$\text{heat transferred} = \sum \text{Power} * \text{time}$$

Storage cycle / utilization cycle

Definition:

Annual charged heat /storage capacity of the TES

Physical meaning: How many cycles has the TES been utilized

One cycle = fully charged then emptied

Typical storage cycle:

1.5 times/year

75,000 m³ water pit heat storage in the Marstal district heating plant

5-6 times/year

60,000 m³ water pit heat storage in the Dronninglund district heating plant

Annual charged heat of the TES \neq Storage capacity of the TES

The benefit of a smart heat storage

Combined renewable technologies and **smart heat storage** interacting with the electricity grid ...

- Smart heat storage:**
- ✓ Gives flexibility
 - ✓ Makes combinations of technologies possible
 - ✓ Use cheap electricity

Source:
<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-78242-213-6.00009-6>

The district heating plant used different heat sources in order to fulfill the heating demand of the district for each hour of the year. The heat sources could be combined heat and power generation (CHP), heat pump, peak boiler, or waste heat and solar heat.

1. District heating network
2. Woodchip/natural gas boiler and combined heat and power generator (CHP)
3. Peak boiler
4. Heat pump
5. Thermal energy storage
6. Heat exchanger
7. Expansion tanks, etc.
8. Other energy source: waste heat, solar heat

Key parameters of a DH:

1. Heating demand
2. Supply temperature
3. Return temperature

DTU Campus will be converted to district heating

Supply and return temperature

Current DH: 3G
 Supply temperature 75-85°C
 Return temperature 35-45°C

District heating from 1G to 4G

District heating demand profile

Household heating demand worldwide

Heating demand of an apartment could be much smaller than the demand of a house

Hourly load: constant base load (for domestic hot water) + variable load (space heating)

Annual base load = 30% annual total heat load = $0.3 * Q$

Annual variable load = 70% annual total heat load = $0.7 * Q$

For Denmark

The annual variable load should be distributed in each hour of the year using degree hour as a weighting factor

Hourly heating demand = $Q * 0.3 / 8760 + Q * 0.7 * (\text{degree hour of the hour}) / \text{Sum of degree hour of the year}$

Hourly heating demand of DH vs. ambient air temperature

ORC = organic Rankine cycle

A schematic drawing of the Marstal solar heating plant, Denmark

3.25 MW Heat output

Woodchip boiler in Marstal district heating

New boiler fuel efficiency 105% (extra 5% due to condensation of flue gas)

Maintenance 5 DKK/GJ heat

Cleaning, waste heat extract

Source: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-78242-213-6.00009-6>

ORC unit in Marstal district heating

Diesel engine in Gram

Natural gas engine in Jærgspris

MW heat output

Typical heat production /electricity production ratio = 7.5/3

Fuel efficiency = (GJ Heat output+GJ electricity output)/GJ Fuel = 75%+30% = 105%

GJ heat /GJ fuel = 75%, GJ fuel /GJ heat = 1/0.75

Heat price = fuel cost per GJ of heat – selling of electricity

Heat price per GJ heat =fuel price(DKK/GJ fuel)*GJ fuel per GJ heat – GJ fuel per GJ heat*0.3*electricity market price
 = fuel price (DKK/GJ fuel) *1/0.75-1/0.75*0.3*electricity market price

Component 3: Peak boiler

Natural gas boiler in Gram district heating

No electricity production

Typical fuel efficiency 95%, maintenance 1 DKK/GJ heat

CO₂ heat pump in Marstal district heating plant

COP (coefficient of performance) is very sensible on the inlet temperature on the hot water circuit (corresponds with the gas cooler outlet temperature) but can reach very high hot water outlet temperatures (~ 80° C) without a reduction of COP.

In Sunstore 4 the temperatures are: inlet 35° C, outlet 80° C

$\text{COP} = \text{Heat output} / \text{electricity consumption}$

For CHP, heat pump, peak boiler, or other heat sources,

Design capacity = max. delivered Power in W or MW (we talk about heat only)

usually determined by the heating demand in the coldest hour

typically, CHP 30%, Heat pump 30%, Peak boiler 40% of the largest hourly heating demand

Heat output = heat quantity in J, GJ or kWh, MWh in a specific period, for example, an hour, a month or a year

Total heat demand of the district heating network = Total heat output of the system

= Heat output from heat pump + output from CHP + output from Peak boiler + other sources

The heat output from individual sources can be 0.

For example, a peak boiler has a larger capacity (40% of total capacity), but its annual heat output might be only 10-20% of the annual total heat demand

Because the peak boiler is expensive and only runs occasionally if other cheaper sources are not available.

Water tank in Ringkøbing DH

Borehole heat storage in Brændstrup DH

Water pit heat storage in Dronninglund DH

Will be discussed in detailed later in the course

Component 6: Heat exchanger

$$T_{S,out} = T_{P,in} - 3$$

$$T_{P,out} = T_{S,in} + 3$$

$$Cp_p m_p = Cp_s m_s \quad m_s = Cp_p m_p / Cp_s$$

Expansion tanks for the solar collector loop

Other energy sources: Waste heat

Energy sources for DH generation in Sweden in 2019. Total: 53.0 TWh

Settlement	Population	Heat energy for DH (GWh/a)	Share of waste heat (%)	Origin of waste heat
Göteborg	580 000	3 650	30%	Various, mainly oil refineries
Varberg	65 000	190	70%	Pulp and paper industry
Luleå	50 000	890	84%	Steel industry
Arvika	26 000	135	6%	Foundry
Ludvika	16 000	136	1%	Unspecified
Bromölla	13 000	50	100%	Ceramic industry
Oxelösund	12 000	100	98%	Steel industry

Issues for use of waste heat: not stable supply

industry process heat could be available with a large amount in a short period

Other energy sources: solar heat

- Issues of use of solar heat:
- Seasonal mismatch with heating demand
- Summer: abundant solar heat but small heating demand
- Winter: insufficient solar heat while larger heating demand

Solar collector field in Klokkeholm og Hjallerup (21546 m²)

<http://www.solvarmedata.dk/>

Principle of solar district heating plant

Exercise for today

1. Please calculate the heat loss coefficients from the top cover, the sides and the bottom surface of the water pit heat storage (W/K) in Marstal. The heat storage volume is 75,000 m³

Assume that the pit heat storage has the shape of a square box with a depth of 10 m and a square bottom surface/top cover. Initially the temperature of the water pit heat storage is uniformly 80°C. There is no charge and discharge of the storage and the storage is left to cool naturally. The heat transfer coefficients of the top cover and the rest surfaces of the store are 0.2 W/m²/K and 0.15 W/m²/K respectively. The temperature of the soil around the store is constantly 12°C. An average ambient air temperature of 10°C can be used in the calculation. The density and the specific heat of water are 985 kg/m³ and 4.2 kJ/kg/K respectively.

2. How many days does it take for the storage temperature to fall down to **75°C**?

3. How many days does it take for the store to reach a heat loss of 10% of its useful energy content? The useful energy content should be calculated with reference to the ambient air temperature.

Source: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-78242-213-6.00009-6>

1. Consider a district heating plant without thermal energy storage, please determine the annual heat production cost of the plant in DKK/MWh.
2. Now the plant plans to install a thermal energy storage, please size the TES based on the heating demand and determine the optimal volume of TES and the lowest heat production cost. Please advise the plant whether it is economically attractive to have a TES. Heat loss from the heat storage can be neglected.
3. Determine dimensions of the water pit heat storage, for example, height, edge sizes.
4. Determine annual heat loss, heat recovery rate and utilization frequency of the PTES
5. Plot heat demand and heat production from various sources over the year.
6. Bonus exercise: parametric investigation and optimization considering at least one of the following factors, for example, fluctuation of natural gas price, electricity market price, waste heat percentage/price, annual heat demand, interest rate, electricity energy storage instead of thermal energy storage, energy flow, etc.

Thanks for your attention

Thermal energy storages

- Design and construction of thermal energy storages

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Last lecture

Standby heat loss and cooling of TES

$$T_{end} = T_a^* + (T_{start} - T_a^*) \exp\left(\frac{-t_{end}(UA_{top} + UA_{soil})}{mC_p}\right)$$

A good example of Danish district energy system for heating and electricity production

Steel tank

Water pit (PTES)

Borehole storage (BTES)

Aquifer storage

COST OF HEAT STORAGE TANKS AND PITS

The soil excavated from the bottom part of the storage is used as embankments around the upper part of the storage.

Large water pit heat storage in DK

SÅDAN BRUGES KORTET

Før musen over byerne for at se den aktuelle status for varmelageret.

Klik på byen for at få flere oplysninger og historiske data.

TILFØJ NYT VARMELAGER

PARTNERE

Energteknologisk udvikling og demonstration

Application of water pit heat storages

2012: Marstal 75,000 m³

1st Design

2015: Vojens 200,000 m³

2nd Design

2013: Dronninglund 62,000 m³

1st Design

2015: Gram 110,000 m³

2nd Design

1st design example: Marstal Solar heating plant

Seasonal heat storage - 75000 m³ PTES

Consumers: 1400

Annual heat consumption: approx. 30 GWh

Central heat plant (biomass boiler, ORC, heat pump etc)

75000 m³ water pit heat storage

Collector field 1: 9043 m²

Collector field 2: 9124 m²

Collector field 3: 15000 m²

1st design example: Construction of PTES in Marstal

1st design example: Construction of the PTES in Dronninglund

2nd design example: Construction of the PTES in Vojens

Construction of PTES: Step 1

Geotechnical investigation of construction site

Underground water level

Landscape

Soil type

Soil property (thermal conductivity, moisture)

Construction of PTES: Step 2 Excavation

Geometry of water pit heat storage

Excavation

Principle: **No soil transportation** away from the construction site

Excavated soil is used to form a dam around the pit

Soil balance

Volume under ground level = volume of the dam around the pit

pyramid

Volume under ground level = truncated pyramid

$$\begin{aligned} V_{\text{underground}} &= \frac{h}{3} (\text{Area 2} + \text{Area 1} + \sqrt{\text{Area 2} * \text{Area 1}}) \\ &= \frac{h}{3} (a^2 + b^2 + a \cdot b) \end{aligned}$$

Edge length of top surface, a

Edge length of top surface, b

Slope, θ [°]

$$\tan(\theta) = \frac{h}{\left(\frac{a}{2} - \frac{b}{2}\right)}$$

$$\left(\frac{a}{2} - \frac{b}{2}\right) = \frac{h}{\tan(\theta)}$$

$$a = b + \frac{2h}{\tan(\theta)}$$

Quadrangular pyramid

Volume under ground level = truncated pyramid

$$V_{\text{underground}} = \frac{h}{6} (a_1 \cdot b_1 + a_2 \cdot b_2 + (a_1 + a_2) \cdot (b_1 + b_2))$$

Soil volume of the embankment

= volume of truncated pyramid 1 – volume of truncated pyramid 2

$$\text{Volume of truncated pyramid 1} = \frac{h_{dam}}{3} (L_{base}^2 + (L_{surface} + 2 \cdot W)^2 + L_{base} \cdot (L_{surface} + 2W))$$

$$\text{Volume of truncated pyramid 2} = \frac{h_{dam}}{3} (L_{surface}^2 + L_{hole}^2 + L_{hole} \cdot L_{surface})$$

Construction of PTES: Step 3 installation of HDPE line layer

Life time and durability of PTES

water	treated, appropriate Ph value, long life time
Line material	cannot stand high temperature (<math><90^{\circ}\text{C}</math>), 20-30 years
Insulation	PE cannot stand high temperature, high humid environment, avoid load, 20-30 years
Pipes, inlet devices	Anti-corrosion treatment

Degradation test of line material

Thermal stratification

Hot

Cold

Auxiliary heat needed

Side view

Inlet/outlet port 1 for higher temperatures

Flow in/out

Inlet/outlet port 2 for medium temperatures

Inlet/outlet port 3 for lower temperatures

Top view

NOTE:

All dimensions in mm
Unless otherwise stated

Rev.	Date	By	Checked/Approved	Project	Task
1	2011-01-28	SSV/SSV	SSV/SSV		

Design of inlet stratifiers

➤ Design guideline: limit of inlet jet flow

Double plate

Stream line

Perforated plate

Baffle

DTU Inlet stratification device: Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) calculations

Photo of the PTES in Marstal

Mesh of the CFD model

CFD model of a water pit storage

Design optimization of a water pit heat storage by Computational fluid dynamics (CFD)

Temperature at the bottom and the side of the storage

Disturbances due to inlet flow showed by vorticity

Thermal stratification in the storage

CFD simulation

Trnsys simulation

Construction of PTES: Step 5 installation of top cover

1,5 mm HDPE Geomembrane
 Hypernet
 80 mm insulation above edge
 Extrusion welding

Hypernet
 2 mm HDPE Geomembrane
 2,5 mm HDPE Geomembrane
 Geotextile 500 g

1st design: Floating layer with foam insulation

Pros:

- Good insulation property
- Water proof, durable
- Can be fixed

Cons:

- Higher installation cost

Cost:

- Relative higher cost, 25-35 Euro/m³ storage volume (large scale)

2nd design: Floating insulation layer with Leca stones

Floating insulation laver

Pros:

- Cheap
- Easy installation
- Insulation material easy to transport

Cons:

- Average insulation property
- Not water proof
- Movement of insulation material

Cost:

- Relative lower cost, 15-25 Euro/m³ storage volume (large scale)

Test of durability and estimation of life time:

- high temperature (>90°C) high humidity (>95%RH) accelerate degradation
- monitoring of insulation property

Arrhenius equation

Lifetime determination by using thermal ageing

PE foam

Water surface area = insulation area on the top

$$= L_{surface}^2$$

Bottom area

$$= L_{bot}^2$$

Area of the sides

$$= 4 \cdot \frac{L_{slope}}{2} (L_{surface} + L_{bot})$$

Heat loss coefficient from different surfaces of the PTES

Ambient Convection+radiation

Water

Heat loss from the top

Heat loss from the sides

Heat loss from the bottom

$$\text{Total heat transfer coefficient} = \frac{1}{\text{Total heat resistance}}$$

k_A Thermal conductivity of layer A
 k_B Thermal conductivity of layer B

Total thermal resistance =
 thermal resistance of layer A + thermal resistance of layer B

$$\text{Total thermal resistance} = \frac{L_A}{k_A} + \frac{L_B}{k_B} \qquad q = \frac{(T1 - T2)}{\left(\frac{L_A}{k_A} + \frac{L_B}{k_B} \right)}$$

$$\text{Total heat transfer coefficient} = \frac{1}{\text{Total heat resistance}}$$

Total heat transfer coefficient =

Radiation heat transfer coefficient + Convection heat transfer coefficient

$$U = h_{rad} + h_{conv}$$

$$\frac{1}{\text{Total thermal resistance}} = \frac{1}{\text{thermal resistance of radiation}} + \frac{1}{\text{thermal resistance of convection}}$$

$$Q_{side} = A_{side} U_{side} (T_{ptes} - T_{soil})$$

$$= A_{side} \frac{1}{\sum R_{side}} (T_{ptes} - T_{soil})$$

$$\sum R_{side} = \frac{t_{side}}{k_{soil}}$$

T_{ptes} Temperature of PTES, °C

T_{soil} Initial soil temperature, °C

t_{side} Thickness of thermally influenced soil layer on the sides of the PTES, typically is difficult to determine [m]

k_{soil} Thermal conductivity [W/(mK)]

$$U_{side} = \frac{1}{\sum R_{side}} = \frac{k_{soil}}{t_{side}}$$

Total thermal resistance $\sum R_{side}$ = thermal resistance of soil material

The same for the bottom surface of the PTES

Heat loss coefficient from the top, U_{top}

$$Q_{top} = A_{top} U_{top} (T_{ptes} - T_a)$$

$$= A_{top} \frac{1}{\sum R_{top}} (T_{ptes} - T_a)$$

$$\sum R_{top} = \frac{t_{top}}{k_{insu}} + \frac{1}{h_e} \quad 4.26$$

T_{ptes} Temperature of PTES, °C

T_a Ambient air temperature, °C

t_{top} Thickness of top insulation [m]

k_b Thermal conductivity [W/(mK)]

h_e Effective heat transfer coefficient from surface to ambient including heat radiation and convection.

$$h_e = h_{convection} + h_{radiation}$$

Total thermal resistance $\sum R_{top} =$

thermal resistance of insulation material + thermal resistance from cover to the ambient

Heat loss coefficient from the top, U_{top}

Heat loss from the cover surface to the ambient: Convection+radiation

$$h_e = h_{convection} + h_{radiation}$$

$$h_{convection} = 5.8 \frac{W}{m^2 K} \quad \text{Wind} = 1 \text{ m/s}$$

$$h_{convection} = 8.8 \frac{W}{m^2 K} \quad \text{Wind} = 2 \text{ m/s}$$

$$h_{radiation} = \frac{\epsilon_{cover} \cdot \sigma \cdot (T_{cover} + T_{sky}) \cdot (T_{cover}^2 + T_{sky}^2) \cdot (T_{cover} - T_{sky})}{(T_{cover} - T_a)}$$

Top heat loss coefficient:

$$U_{top} = \frac{1}{\sum R_{top}} = \frac{1}{\frac{t_{top}}{k_{insu}} + \frac{1}{h_e}} \quad T_{cover} \text{ unknown}$$

Stefan-Boltzmann constant $\sigma = 5.6697 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K}^4)$

Calculation of heat loss coefficient from the top, U_{top}

- Step 1: guess T_{cover}

- Step 2: calculate $h_{radiation}$

Use the new T_{cover}

$$h_{radiation} = \frac{\varepsilon_{cover} \cdot \sigma \cdot (T_{cover} + T_{sky}) \cdot (T_{cover}^2 + T_{sky}^2) \cdot (T_{cover} - T_{sky})}{(T_{cover} - T_a)}$$

- Step 3: solve T_{cover}

$$q_{step1} = \frac{K_{insu}}{t_{top}} (T_{ptes} - T_{cover})$$

$$q_{step2} = (h_{convection} + h_{radiation}) (T_{cover} - T_a)$$

Steady state $q_{step1} = q_{step2}$

$$T_{cover} = \frac{\frac{K_{insu}}{t_{top}} T_{ptes} + (h_{convection} + h_{radiation}) T_a}{\frac{K_{insu}}{t_{top}} + h_{convection} + h_{radiation}}$$

If $T_{cover} = T_a$

Don't use U_{top} , since $h_{radiation}$ is not valid any more

- Step 1: guess T_{cover}
- Step 2: calculate $h_{radiation}$

Use the new T_{cover}

$$Q_{radiation} = \varepsilon_{cover} \cdot \sigma \cdot (T_{cover} + T_{sky}) \cdot (T_{cover}^2 + T_{sky}^2) \cdot (T_{cover} - T_{sky})$$

- Step 3: solve T_{cover}

$$q_{step1} = \frac{K_{insu}}{t_{top}} (T_{ptes} - T_{cover})$$

$$q_{step2} = (h_{convection})(T_{cover} - T_a) + Q_{radiation}$$

Steady state $q_{step1} = q_{step2}$

Solve the equation to obtain T_{cover}

Heat loss from the cover = $q_{step1} = q_{step2}$

Don't use U_{top}

Rain water drainage design of the lid (top cover)

- Pipe dimension
- Ø 90 mm
 - Ø 110 mm
 - Ø 125 mm
 - Ø 140 mm
 - Ø 160 mm
 - Ø 315 mm

Rain water collection and drainage

1st design

PlanEnergi

PTES in Dronninglund

Side channels

Main channels

Rain water collection
Pump station

Small ponds of rain water on lid

Small pond of rain water

Manual drainage of water necessary

pH values of water in PTES > 10

Filter of dirt /debris

Anti-corrosion measures

Hot water tank for district heating systems

Design of steel hot water tank

Side view

AutoCAD drawing

Typical hot water tank volume < 7000 m³

Hot water tank for district heating systems with CHP

Heat storage tank example 1

Pressureless direct connection

- Optimize CHP
- Optimize DH system
- Can be designed to cold water
- Integrate large-scale solar 20%
- All CHP plants have heat storage tanks in Denmark
- Fynsværket power plant, Odense
 - 70,000 m³,
 - 4 GWh, e.g. 500 MW 8 hours
 - Direct connection
 - Maximum temp 95°C. 90/40

Heat storage tank example 2

Pressurized and pressure sectioned

- Higher temperature can be necessary due to consumer needs (poor heating installations)
- Pressure section can be necessary due to operation of the DH grid
- Avedøre CHP plant, Copenhagen
 - 2 x 24,000 m³,
 - 3 GWh, 300 MW in 10 h
 - Maximal temp 120 °C 105/50
 - Direct connection, pressure section
 - Pressure diff: 10 Bar

Operation and control of hot water tank for CHP

Source: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2015.10.027>

Key component: inlet stratifier

The Condat tank

ANSYS
2019 R2
ACADEMIC

The CFD model

Temperature distribution in the tank during charge in a cloudy day

The aim is to minimize the mixing caused by inlet jet flow

Design of inlet stratification devices for hot water tank

Direct inlet

Bent

T-piece

Perforated pipe

Parallel plates

The aim is to minimize mixing caused by water entering the tank

Inlet	Maximum volume flow rate without mixing
2" bent	1000 l/h
2" direct inlet	1800 l/h
2" perforated plate	1800 l/h
2" T-piece	2500 l/h
2" parallel plates	4500 l/h

CFD model of a hot water tank

Heat loss coefficients of hot water tank, U_{st}

$$U_{\text{tank top}} = \frac{\frac{\pi}{4} (d_y + e_s)^2}{\frac{e_t}{\lambda} + \frac{1}{a_{\text{top}}}} \quad \text{W/K}$$

$$U_{\text{tank side}} = \frac{\pi}{\frac{1}{2\lambda} \ln \frac{d_y + 2e_s}{d_y} + \frac{1}{a_{\text{side}}}} \frac{1}{d_y + 2e_s} H \quad \text{W/K}$$

$$U_{\text{tank bottom}} = \frac{\frac{\pi}{4} (d_y + e_s)^2}{\frac{e_b}{\lambda} + \frac{1}{a_{\text{bot}}}} \quad \text{W/K}$$

d_y : outer diameter of the tank.

H : height of the tank.

a_{top} , a_{bot} , a_{side} : heat transfer coefficient of the top (10 W/m²K), the bottom 5.88 W/m²K and the side surface of the tank (7.69 W/m²K) respectively.

Insulation, thermal conductivity λ

Insulation thickness e_t, e_s, e_b

1. Please calculate geometry of the water pit heat storage in Marstal (75,000 m³)

Assume that the pit heat storage has the shape of a truncated pyramid a depth of 10 m and a square bottom surface/top cover. The width of the walk way of the dam is 3 meters.

2. Please calculate heat loss coefficient of the PTES in W/m²/K for the top cover, the sides and the bottom surface respectively, calculate total heat loss of the PTES in W.

Initially the temperature of the water pit heat storage is uniformly 80°C. The ambient air is 5°C and the sky temperature is 10 K lower than the temperature of ambient air. The initial soil temperature (outside of the thermal influenced layer) is 10°C. At a steady state condition the thermally influenced layer of soil around the PTES is 30 m thick.

Thermal conductivity of soil around the PTES is constantly 0.7 W/m/K.

The top cover has a PE insulation layer of 0.25 m. The thermal conductivity of PE is 0.045 W/m/K. An average wind speed over the PTES of 1 m/s can be assumed.

Emissivity of the cover is 0.2.

The slope of the water pit is 26.6°

Operation of TES in a district heating system

Firstly, for each hour of the year, determine heat cost for CHP, Heat pump and Peak boiler, waste heat (already given)

Charge of heat storage: if the heat cost is cheap enough (defined as a parameter, different threshold values could be tried), the heat could be stored in TES. Respect the limits of capacity for CHP, Heat pump, etc. (That means the output should always be within the max. capacity)

The plant operator should choose the right heat source and charge/discharge of the TES

For an example,

Waste heat is most of the time the cheapest, therefore 1st priority

Heat from TES will be cheaper than heat price of heat pump and CHP, therefore 2nd priority

Depending on electricity price, heat pump or CHP should be selected as the 3rd priority

Peak boiler is the most expensive, therefore the last priority, only to cover the demand cannot be covered

For the TES, in each hour, calculate charged/discharged hot water volume (80C) and converted into loss of hot water volume (80C)

Tips for the Assignment

- **Solution guideline for the assignment**

Question 1: for each hour of the year, determine heat cost for CHP, Heat pump and Peak boiler. The cost of heat production is calculated by summarizing the hourly costs over the year.

Question 2: Considering heat storage (no matter whether it is hot water tank or water pit)

For each hour of the year,

If there is excess heat (heat production > consumption), the surplus heat storage will be stored in TES.

If there is a lack of heat (heat production < consumption), stored heat will be taken from TES.

The charged/discharged hot water volumes (80C) are converted into gain/loss of hot water volumes (from 40C to 80C or vice versa) in the TES. The hot water volume in TES must be tracked.

The required heat storage volume is the max. hourly calculated hot water volume in TES in the year. Heat loss from TES can be neglected when answering this question.

Based on the volume of TES, either a hot water tank or a water pit will be chosen based on construction cost. The levelized cost of heat (LCOH) is then recalculated, considering the costs of waste heat and heat storage. The LCOH will be the lowest if the cheapest TES design is chosen.

Questions 3, 4 and 5, 6:

For Question 4, consider heat loss (consequently loss of hot water volume 80C) for each hour and sum all hourly heat loss to obtain the annual heat loss from the TES

Note: Fuel use profiles already given (not allowed to change), no need to optimize fuel use.

The given heat productions must be utilized (either stored in TES or used directly for district heating).

Thanks for your attention!

Thermal energy storages

- Thermal stratification and system integration

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$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\lambda}{\rho c_p} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2}$$

$\Delta \int_a^b \epsilon \Theta^{\sqrt{17}} + \Omega \int \delta e^{i\pi} =$
 $\infty = \{2.7182818284\}$
 $\chi^2 \Sigma !$

Lecture 10:

- Overview of heat storage technologies
- Latent heat storage and sensible heat storage
- Introduction to the assignment

Lecture 11:

- Design of water pit heat storage
- Design of hot water tank

Lecture 12:

- System integration of TES in the energy systems
- Economical analysis and optimization

Lecture 13:

- Thermal performance of water pit heat storages
- Simulation models of TES
- Summary of the four lectures on TES
- Course evaluation

pyramid

Volume under ground level = truncated pyramid

$$\begin{aligned} V_{\text{underground}} &= \frac{h}{3} (\text{Area 2} + \text{Area 1} + \sqrt{\text{Area 2} * \text{Area 1}}) \\ &= \frac{h}{3} (a^2 + b^2 + a \cdot b) \end{aligned}$$

Heat loss from PTES

Heat loss coefficient from the side and the bottom:

$$Q_{side} = A_{side} U_{side} (T_{ptes} - T_{soil}) \qquad U_{side} = \frac{1}{\sum R_{side}} = \frac{k_{soil}}{t_{side}}$$

Heat loss coefficient from the cover:

$$Q_{top} = A_{top} U_{top} (T_{ptes} - T_a) \qquad U_{top} = \frac{1}{\sum R_{top}} = \frac{1}{\frac{t_{top}}{k_{insu}} + \frac{1}{h_e}}$$

$$h_e = h_{convection} + h_{radiation}$$

$$h_{convection} = 5.8 \frac{W}{m^2 K} \qquad \text{Wind} = 1 \text{ m/s}$$

$$h_{convection} = 8.8 \frac{W}{m^2 K} \qquad \text{Wind} = 2 \text{ m/s}$$

$$h_{radiation} = \frac{\varepsilon_{cover} \cdot \sigma \cdot (T_{cover} + T_{sky}) \cdot (T_{cover}^2 + T_{sky}^2) \cdot (T_{cover} - T_{sky})}{(T_{cover} - T_a)}$$

Iteration is needed to determine Q_{top}

Heat loss coefficients of hot water tank, U_{st}

$$U_{\text{tank top}} = \frac{\frac{\pi}{4} (d_y + e_s)^2}{\frac{e_t}{\lambda} + \frac{1}{\alpha_{top}}} \quad \text{W/K}$$

$$U_{\text{tank side}} = \frac{\pi}{\frac{1}{2\lambda} \ln \frac{d_y + 2e_s}{d_y} + \frac{1}{\alpha_{side}} \frac{1}{d_y + 2e_s}} H \quad \text{W/K}$$

$$U_{\text{tank bottom}} = \frac{\frac{\pi}{4} (d_y + e_s)^2}{\frac{e_b}{\lambda} + \frac{1}{\alpha_{bot}}} \quad \text{W/K}$$

d_y : outer diameter of the tank.
 H : height of the tank.
 α_{top} , α_{bot} , α_{side} : heat transfer coefficient of the top (10 W/m²K), the bottom 5.88 W/m²K and the side surface of the tank (7.69 W/m²K) respectively.

Insulation, thermal conductivity λ
 Insulation thickness e_t , e_s , e_b

Cause:

- Water density is temperature dependent
- Higher water temperature → Lower density → Upper part of the TES
- Lower water temperature → Higher density → Lower part of the TES

Benefit:

- Higher temperature in upper part of TES → lower auxiliary energy consumption
- Lower temperature in lower part of TES → Higher renewable energy efficiency
- Overall, higher system efficiency

How to maintain thermal stratification in TES:

- Correct Inlet/outlet placement: cold water inlet/outlet at the bottom
- Diffuser designs to minimize mixing due to water inlet

Thermal stratification in thermal energy storage

The cause of mixing in PTES

- Internal mixing (due to fluid motion and conduction)
- Pit top cover heat losses (to ambient)
- Fluid and tank wall conduction is of interest mainly for long term stores (days or longer)
- For short term stores (hours), the efficiency is dominated by internal mixing

Fundamentals

1. law of thermodynamics: conservation of energy

- Energy analysis of an energy conversion system is essentially an accounting of the energies entering and leaving → Energy efficiency

2. law of thermodynamics: degradation of the energy quality

- Exergy analysis acknowledges that, although energy cannot be created or destroyed, it can be degraded in quality

Internal mixing (due to fluid motion)

Potential energy is the energy that is stored in an object due to its position relative to some zero position. Kinetic energy is a form of energy that an object has by reason of its motion. Layer height H = height from the middle of the layer to the storage bottom

Internal mixing (due to fluid motion)

No mixing

Mixing of two layers

Mixing of three layers

H [m]	T [°C]	E_{pot}	T [°C]	E_{pot}	T [°C]	E_{pot}
0.9	60	8675.879	60	8675.879	60	8675.879
0.7	50	6778.108	50	6778.108	50	6778.108
0.5	40	4859.309	40	4859.309	30	4873.342
0.3	30	2924.005	25	2927.367	30	2924.005
0.1	20	976.721	25	975.789	30	974.668
		24214.02		24216.45		24226

(+2.43)

(+11.98)

Incoming kinetic energy

$$E_{kin} = 0.5 \cdot \rho \cdot v^2$$

Potential energy in the store

$$E_{pot} = \rho \cdot g \cdot H$$

The best

The worst

Incoming kinetic energy is transformed to potential energy in the store and frictional heat (neglectable)

Internal mixing (due to fluid motion)

If TES temperature increases from 20-60°C to 20-80°C

H [m]	T [°C]	E_{pot}	T [°C]	E_{pot}	T [°C]	E_{pot}
0.9	80	8577.845	80	8577.845	80	8577.845
0.7	70	6712.42	70	6712.42	70	6712.42
0.5	60	4819.931	60	4819.931	36.66	4864.406
0.3	30	2924.005	25	2927.367	36.66	2918.643
0.1	20	976.721	25	975.789	36.66	972.881
		24010.92		24013.35		24046.19

(+2.43)

(+35.27)

The smallest potential energy E_{pot}
No mixing

The largest E_{pot}
The largest mixing

- It takes more energy to mix over a strong thermocline (large ΔT)

Characterization of stratification

No measurements required inside the storage

- Charge/discharge efficiency
- Richardson number
- Froude number

Measurements required inside the storage

- Moment of energy and MIX number
- Exergy analysis

Charge/discharge efficiency

Charge

$$Q_1 = \int_{t_{start}}^{t_{stop}} V \cdot \rho \cdot c_p \cdot (T_{inlet} - T_{outlet}) \cdot dt \quad [J]$$

$$Q_2 = V \cdot \rho \cdot c_p \cdot (T_{average,inlet} - T_{initial}) \quad [J]$$

Discharge

$$Q_1 = \int_{t_{start}}^{t_{stop}} V \cdot \rho \cdot c_p \cdot (T_{outlet} - T_{inlet}) \cdot dt \quad [J]$$

$$Q_2 = V \cdot \rho \cdot c_p \cdot (T_{initial} - T_{average,inlet}) \quad [J]$$

Q_1	actual energy amount supplied to the tank	[J]
Q_2	maximum possible exchanged energy amount	[J]
V	exchanged tank volume	[m ³]
\dot{V}	volume flow rate	[m ³ /s]
$T_{initial}$	initial tank temperature	[° C]
T_{inlet}	inlet temperature	[° C]
T_{outlet}	outlet temperature	[° C]
$T_{average,inlet}$	average inlet temperature during the experiment	[° C]
c_p	water heat capacity	[J/kg·K]
ρ	water density	[kg/m ³]

$$\eta = \frac{Q_1}{Q_2}$$

Richardson number

$$Ri = \frac{Gr}{Re^2} = \frac{g \cdot \beta \cdot \Delta T \cdot L^3}{\nu^2 \left(\frac{u \cdot L}{\nu} \right)^2} = \frac{Boyancy}{Inertia}$$

- Boyancy forces promote stratification
- Inertia forces destroy stratification

β is the temperature expansion coefficient [K^{-1}]

ν is the kinematic viscosity [m^2/s]

g is the gravity [m/s^2]

ΔT is the temperature difference between inlet water and the tank water at the inlet [K]

u is the inlet velocity in the inlet pipe [m/s]

L is the diameter of the inlet pipe

Froude number

- Inertia force on an element of fluid to the weight of the fluid element
- Influence of gravity on fluid motion

$$Fr_i = \frac{q}{\sqrt{\frac{h_i^3 \cdot g \cdot \Delta\rho_i}{\rho_i}}}$$

q is the flow rate per unit length of diffuser into the circumferential direction [m^2/s]

h_i is the height of the diffuser [m]

g is the gravity [m/s^2]

$\Delta\rho_i$ is the density difference between the inlet water and the tank water

ρ_i is the density of the inlet water

v_i is the average velocity magnitude of the inlet jet flow just leaving the inlet opening

General recommendation: $Fr_i \leq 2$

Another recommendation: $v_{i,\text{average}} < 3 \text{ cm/s}$

Moment of energy analysis – MIX number

$$MIX = \frac{M_{str} - M_{exp}}{M_{str} - M_{mix}}$$

- T_{str} = the charging temperature
- T_{start} = the cold water temperature
- T_{exp} = measure water temperature
- T_{mix} = water temperature if fully mixed

Moment of energy analysis – MIX number

E_i , the energy content of the i th layer, T_i Temperature of the layer, T_{ref} , the reference (cold water) temperature, V_i volume of the layer, ρ , c density and specific heat of water respectively, y_i is the height from the i th layer middle to storage bottom

Exergy analysis

- Exergy change during charge or discharge

$$\Delta \xi = c_p \sum_{j=1}^{j=N} \left(m_j \cdot (T_j - T_0) + m_j \cdot T_0 \cdot \ln \left(\frac{T_0}{T_j} \right) \right)$$

$$\eta_{\xi} = \frac{\Delta \xi_{\text{experiment}}}{\Delta \xi_{\text{ideal}}}$$

j is the layer number

m_j is the mass of control volume 'j'

T_j is the temperatur of control volume 'j'

T₀ is the reference temperature (constant cold water temperature in discharge test and start temperature in charge test)

c_p is the specific heat capacity

N is the number of layers

Better thermal stratification in the TES means:

- Higher charge/discharge efficiency
- Higher Richardson number for inlet
- Lower Froude number for inlet
- Lower MIX number
- Higher exergy efficiency

$$\frac{(T - T_{\text{start}})}{(T_{\text{inlet}} - T_{\text{start}})}$$

Advantage

**Small differences in start temperatures
and inlet temperatures are eliminated
→ comparison possible**

Two different stratifiers

Two different stratifiers

Dimensionless temperature, time, volume and height

- Dimensionless time: $t/t_{\text{experiment}}$
- Dimensionless volume: $V_{\text{tap}}/V_{\text{tank}}$
- Dimensionless height: Height/Tank height

Literature on characterization of thermal stratification

- [Methods to determine stratification efficiency of thermal energy storage processes–Review and theoretical comparison.](#) / Haller, Michel; Cruickshank, Chynthia; Streicher, Wolfgang; Harrison, Stephen J.; [Andersen, Elsa; Furbo, Simon.](#)
In: [Solar Energy](#), Vol. 83, No. 10, 2009, p. 1847-1860.

Simplified TES with perfect thermal stratification

Full TES

Half full TES

Empty TES

Only two temperatures possible in TES: 40C or 80C

Charge of TES = water volume heated from 40C to 80C

Heat loss /heat discharged (tapped) from TES = water volume cooled from 80C to 40C

General equation:

$$Q = \rho \cdot c \cdot \Delta T \cdot V$$

Q	Heat content of storage	(Joule)
ρ	Density of water	(kg/m ³)
c	Specific heat of water	(J/(kg· °C))
ΔT	Temperature difference of water	(K)
V	Water volume	(m ³)

temperature difference, ΔT = Hot water temperature stored – reference temperature

For district heating, the reference T = the return T from the consumers (40°C)
Hot water temperature stored = Supply temperature of district heating (80°C)

Conversion of energy units:

1 kWh = 3600*1000 J = 3.6*10⁶ J = 3.6 MJ

1 MWh= 3.6 GJ

Change of energy content of the tank, ΔE , kWh
 Or Change of hot water (80C) volume, m³

Energy charged, kWh
 Or hot water volume, m³

Tapped energy, E_{tap} , kWh

Or hot water volume, m³

$$\Delta E = E_{charged} - E_{tap} - E_{heat\ loss}$$

TES heat loss, kW·h
 Or hot water volume, m³

System integration of TES

System integration into a district heating system

Solution 1: short term heat storage

Typically volume < 7000 m³
Storage time: up to 2 weeks

Solution 1 example: Jægerspris Combined Heat & Power (CHP), Denmark

Water storage tanks - 5000 m³

Consumers: 1332

Annual heat consumption: approx. 27 GWh

Over Dråby

Jægerspris
Kraftvarme Amba

3000 m³ + 2*1000 m³ water tanks

Koatek A/S

Central heat plant (gas CHP,
absorption heat pump etc)

Jægerspris Genbrugsplads

Daily/Week heat storage

Collector field: 13,400 m²

System integration into a district heating system

Solution 2: long term heat storage

Solar fraction up to 50%

DTU Solution 2 Examples: Solar district heating systems in China

A Danish made solar heating system in China

3.1 Project Progress

- ✓ Solar field:
 - ✓ 1620 collectors
 - ✓ Pipeline & valves
 - ✓ Signal lines

- ✓ Storage:
 - ✓ Main body
 - ✓ Protection slope and fence (To be completed)

- ✓ HX station and technical room
 - ✓ HX station
 - ✓ Charge/discharge unit
 - ✓ Water treatment
 - Control system (To be completed)
- ✓ Equipment house
 - ✓ High&low voltage supply
 - ✓ Electrical boiler
 - ✓ Diesel generator
- ✓ DH-grid & heating terminals
- ✓ 82,600 m² covering 26 residential communities

Heat only, no electricity production
Solar fraction almost 100%
No heat pump installed

System integration into a district heating system

Solution 3: solar+CHP

CHP: Combined heat and power production
 Fuel: gas, diesel, woodchip or other biomass

Marstal Solar heating plant

Seasonal heat storage - 75000 m³ PTES

Consumers: 1600

Annual heat consumption: approx. 30 GWh

Hot water tank
2000 m³

Central heat plant (biomass
boiler, ORC, heat pump etc)

75000 m³ water pit heat storage

Collector field 1: 9043 m²

Collector field 2: 9124 m²

Collector field 3: 15000 m²

	Jan 2015	Feb 2015	Mar 2015	Apr 2015	May 2015	Jun 2015	Jul 2015	Aug 2015	Sep 2015	Oct 2015	Nov 2015	Dec 2015
■ Oil Boilers	32	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
■ Electricity consumption Heat Pump	140	232	113	7	41	33	0	0	0	0	70	36
■ Discharging S4 PTES	1018	672	230	20	485	314	159	140	469	660	678	589
■ Biomass Boiler + ORC	2804	2513	2595	2210	703	0	9	0	0	1251	1737	2678
■ Solar Collectors	89	317	1144	2098	1784	1886	1919	1811	1282	518	116	26
■ Charging S4 PTES	22	111	659	1813	1214	974	1074	995	584	312	52	2
■ Sunmark cooling	0	103	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0
■ Total heat supply	4239	4035	3456	2535	1868	1253	1013	900	1134	2215	2919	3475

Average COP = 3.3

Heat pump inlet temperature 40C, outlet temperature = 75C

Heat source: from PTES, 25-65C, back to PTES 20-30C

Monitored year: 2015
 Solar fraction: 41%
 RES fraction: 100%
 Solar gain: 395 kWh/m²/year

Blue number: Design values
 Black number: monitored values
 in MWh/year

- ☐ Solar fraction: 35 %
- ☐ RE fraction: 100 %

- ☐ Storage efficiency: 69%
- ☐ T-min: 20 ° C
- ☐ T-max: 82 ° C

Number of storage cycle = 1.5

Storage efficiency = heat recovery rate = (annual discharged heat + TES content change)/annual charged heat
 Number of storage cycles = utilization frequency = annual charged heat/ TES capacity

63000 m³ PTES

Technical room (heat exchanger, pumps, control room, etc)

Pipe to the consumer

37573 m² solar collector field

There is no short term heat storage tank

Example: Dronninglund

- Project: *Follow up on large scale heat storages in Denmark* funded by the Energy Technology Development and Demonstration Program
- Heat losses, efficiency and feasibility depend highly on the use of the storage
- Preliminary results from this project (source: Solites):

Pit storage | energy flow year 2014 - 2016

Storage efficiency:	90 %	T-max:	89 °C
No. of storage cycles:	6.0	T-min:	12 °C
Heat capacity (80 K):	5 500 MWh		

The larger the number of storage cycles, the larger the storage efficiency

Note: Number of storage cycles = annual charged heat/ TES capacity

Monitoring results 2014 - 2016, numbers in MWh/a

Example: Dronninglund

- Project: *Follow up on large scale heat storages in Denmark* funded by the Energy Technology Development and Demonstration Program
- Heat losses, efficiency and feasibility depend highly on the use of the storage
- Preliminary results from this project (source: Solites):

Pit storage | energy balance 2015

The world largest PTES

- Heat storage pit:
 - 122,000 m³
 - Green field
 - Maximal temp 85 °C
 - Pressure sep. by heat exchanger
 - 44.000 m² solar panels
 - 60% share of solar heat

70,000 m³ water pit heat storage for waste heat

- 19 cities
- 4 district energy systems
- 160 km. heating pipe
- 25 district heating companies
- 500,000 consumers
- 34,500 TJ (9,600 GWh)
- 20% of Danish heat consumption

1

2

3

Constructed: 2022

Volume: 70,000 m³

Capacity: 3.3 GWh

Storage temperature: 90° C

Utilization frequency: 20-30/a

Charg/discharge power: 30 MW

Fossil fuels together: 38%

Biofuels: straw, wood-chips, wood pallet/waste, bio-oil, bio-gas, bio-waste

Renewable: solar, geothermal

Typical heat price for district heating consumers: 500-700 DKK/MWh inclusive the costs : heat production cost (fuel cost, operation/maintenance, tax), capital investment, grid heat loss (20-25%)

District heating companies: non-profit, collective consumer owned

Strategy of the district heating companies:

- 1. Secure stable supply of heat (hourly demand fully covered by DH)
- 2. Decrease heating cost for the consumers by choosing the cheapest heating source

Heating by CHP: Heat cost = (fuel cost + tax) – sell of electricity

Heating by heat pump: Heat cost = (electricity market price + tax) / COP

Heating by peak boiler (natural gas/oil): Heat cost = (fuel cost + tax)

In addition, the maintenance costs should be considered.

Tax is very high for fossil fuel

Heat cost highly dependent on electricity price

Electricity consumption is only 1/3 of heating consumption

If all heat is provided using heat pump, the electricity grid must be 2-3 times larger

The variable cost of heat production depends on electricity prices

The figure is only shown as an example.
Heat production cost changes from year to year

Storage types, design
 Storage volume
 Cost benefit analysis

Limited cost data is available for the implementation of borehole thermal energy storages. The figure shows the specific cost for installed and conceptual BTES. It is clear that the specific cost drops significantly as the size increases.

Heat capacity of soil is significant lower than for water (factor around 4)

Cost of thermal energy storages – Pit heat storage

> 100 000 m³ → costs approx. 30 €/m³:

Hot water tank vs. Water pit

Other heat sources: Solar heating

FP solar collectors take the largest share of European solar heating market

Source: Visual Dictionary Online Website, 2009 www.visualdictionaryonline.com

DTU
Array layout of solar collector field

collector area 7000 m²

Almere (Netherlands), SUNMARK
Constructed in 2010

Phase 1: c

Brædstrup

- Pumps P1 and P2 (primary and secondary sides of the solar HX) start according to the same control strategy previously described.
- P1 and P2 are regulated so that the setpoint for T4 is reached. When the solar production covers the DH demand, the setpoint for T4 is set to the desired temperature in the storage (for example 90 °C).

Solar collector field integration with respect to the previous heating plant in Brødstrup

Real heat prices solarheatdata.eu

Specific investment versus construction year

Heat price versus size of collector field

Waste heat could be cheap

Waste heat potential per industrial sector in the EU

Carnot's potential per industrial sector in the EU

Source:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319942698_Preliminary_assessment_of_waste_heat_potential_in_major_European_industries

Source: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2013.06.104>.

Industry

District heating plant

Consumers

Peak shaving using large scale thermal energy storage is necessary

Source: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2013.06.104>.

$$LCoH = \frac{I_0 - S_0 + \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{C_t(1 - TR) - DEP_t \cdot TR}{(1 + r)^t} - \frac{RV}{(1 + r)^T}}{\sum_{t=1}^T \frac{E_t}{(1 + r)^t}}$$

LCoH: the levelized cost of heat, DKK / kWh;

I_0 : the initial investment for the system, DKK;

S_0 : subsidies and incentives, DKK;

C_t : operation (fuel) and maintenance costs (in year t), DKK;

TR : the corporate tax rate, %;

DEP_t : the asset depreciation (year t), DKK;

RV : the residual value of system;

E_t : the total energy demand (in year t), kWh;

r : the discount rate, %;

T : the period of analysis, year.

No subsidies/incentives

corporate tax rate, asset depreciation, the discount rate are not considered

The residual value of the system after the life time is zero.

Lift time of the system is 20 years

$$LCoH = \frac{I_0 + 20C_t}{20E_t} = \frac{\frac{I_0}{20} + C_t}{E_t}$$

If there is a bank loan for the capital investment, the annual payment of the loan could be considered

$$LCoH = \frac{itr * I_0 + 20C_t}{20E_t} = \frac{\frac{itr * I_0}{20} + C_t}{E_t}$$

The annual payment of the loan ($itr * I_0 / 20$) consists of:

1. Principal payment: pay off the investment cost of the system, I_0
2. Interest payment

Annual payment of a loan ($\text{itr}/20 \cdot I_0$)

What is the annual payment?

Interest = 0%, 20 year loan

Annual payment $\text{itr}/20 = 1/20 + 0\% = 5\%$

How to use the following table?

Annual interest rate is 1%

Annual payment $\text{itr}/20 = 5.5415\%$

Annual interest rate	Annual payment/Amount of loan, %
1.0%	-5.5415%
1.5%	-5.8246%
2.0%	-6.1157%
2.5%	-6.4147%
3.0%	-6.7216%
3.5%	-7.0361%
4.0%	-7.3582%
4.5%	-7.6876%
5.0%	-8.0243%

Exercise-Analysis of the measurement data of the PTES in Marstal

The PTES is divided into 32 layers of equal height (0.5 m), each layer with a temperature sensor. Temperatures of the layers were measured on April 1 and April 28, see the attached measurement data on DTU Learn. Assume that the design of the PTES is the same as the PTES in the last exercise except the depth of the PTES, which is 16 meters now.

The average charging temperature is 72.3°C while the cold water temperature is 26.7°C .

1. For the start of the period, April 01, please calculate the momentum of energy if the PTES is fully mixed, calculate the momentum of energy if the PTES is perfectly stratified, calculate the measured momentum of energy, calculate MIX number.
2. The storage is charged in April. Calculate the MIX number at the end of the charging period on April 28

Thanks for your attention!

Thermal performance analysis of PTES

- Measurement and numerical analysis

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$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\lambda}{\rho c_p} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2}$$

$\Delta \int_a^b \epsilon \Theta^{\sqrt{17}} + \Omega \int \delta e^{i\pi} =$
 $\infty = \{2.7182818284\}$
 $\chi^2 \Sigma !$

Lecture 10:

- Overview of heat storage technologies
- Latent heat storage and sensible heat storage
- Introduction to the assignment

Lecture 11:

- Design of water pit heat storage
- Design of hot water tank

Lecture 12:

- System integration of TES in the energy systems
- Economical analysis and optimization

Lecture 13:

- Thermal performance of water pit heat storages
- Simulation models of TES
- Summary of the four lectures on TES
- Course evaluation

Recap of lecture 12 – MIX number

$$MIX = \frac{M_{str} - M_{exp}}{M_{str} - M_{mix}}$$

- T_{str} = the charging temperature
- T_{start} = the cold water temperature
- T_{exp} = measure water temperature
- T_{mix} = water temperature if fully mixed

Better thermal stratification in the TES means:

- Higher charge/discharge efficiency
- Higher Richardson number for inlet
- Lower Froude number for inlet
- Lower MIX number
- Higher exergy efficiency

District heating companies:

- 1. Secure stable supply of heat (hourly demand fully covered by DH)
- 2. Decrease heating cost for the consumers by choosing the cheapest heating source

The variable cost of heat production depends on electricity prices

Thermal performance of PTES

Key questions:

- How is thermal stratification preserved during operation?
 - Inlet diffuser design: Max velocities → Addressed in lecture no. 11 & 12
 - Charging /discharging strategy
 - Flow patterns (inlet mixing)
- Which are the most significant heat loss sources and how are these losses distributed?
 - heat loss from PTES: Lid, side and bottom
 - Ground conditions
- Alternative stratification arrangement
 - A simpler large diameter horizontal pipe, is tested and compared

Will be addressed today

Will be addressed today

Keep good thermal stratification in TES:

- Higher temperature ↔ TES top
- Lower temperature ↔ TES bottom

	Water pit storage, Marstal	Water pit storage, Dronninglund	Water pit storage, Gram
Size	75000 m ³ water	62000 m ³ water	110000 m ³ water
Maximum storage temperature	90°C	90°C	90°C
Heat recovered from heat storage during first year	18%	78%	55%
Heat recovered from heat storage during second year	65%	90%	
Heat recovered from heat storage during third year	62%	91%	
Storage cycle (utilization frequency)	1-2	4-5	

Cover design

Inlet/outlet design

Water body design

Monitoring of PTES in Dronninglund 2014-2017

Annual heat recovery rate Mean value 92%, max value >95%

Energy flow of the PTES in Dronninglund

Temperature in PTES

Monitoring of PTES in Dronninglund show that

- 1. High heat recovery rate >95%
- 2. temperature of PTES stable

Temperature in PTES in Dronninglund 2015-2019

Dronninglund PTES

Full scale 3D model developed in ANSYS

Prototype

Dronninglund PTES measurement setup

Parameters	Maximum temperature (°C)	Minimum PTES temperature (°C)	Heat capacity (MWh)	Charged energy (MWh)	Discharged energy (MWh)	Internal energy change (MWh)	Heat loss (MWh)	Storage efficiency (%)	Storage cycle
Measured	84.4	8.7	5153	11,565	11,089	-594	1070	90.5	2.1
Simulated	85.8	8.2	5281	11,625	11,184	-569	1009	91.3	2.1
Deviation	1.4 K	0.5 K	2.5%	0.5%	0.9%	4.2%	5.7%	0.7%	0.0%

Mixing due the inlet jet flow in a hot water tank

Buoyancy jet in the water pit heat storage

Uniform temperature in PTES

$$\theta = \frac{T_t - T_0}{T_{in} - T_0}$$

T_{in} : Inflow temperature
 T_0 : PTES initial temperature
 T_t : PTES temperature at time t

Penetration height for a positive buoyancy jet

$$M(\text{Momentum}) = \pi D_h^2 v^2$$

$$F(\text{Buoyancy flux}) = \pi \left[\frac{g(\rho_{in} - \rho_0)}{\rho_0} \right] D_h^2 v$$

$$Z \cdot M^{(-\frac{3}{4})} \cdot |F|^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot 10^{(-3)}$$

$$= \begin{cases} 0.044 \cdot \left(\frac{t \cdot |F| \cdot 10^{(-3)}}{M} \right)^{1.16} & Re \leq 1292 \\ 0.123 \cdot \left(\frac{t \cdot |F| \cdot 10^{(-3)}}{M} \right)^{0.78} & Re > 1292 \end{cases}$$

Figure. Variation of the penetration height with time for a positive buoyancy jet under different operation conditions

$$Z \cdot M^{(-\frac{3}{4})} \cdot |F|^{(\frac{1}{2})} \cdot 10^{(-3)}$$

$$= \begin{cases} 0.085 \cdot \left(\frac{t \cdot |F| \cdot 10^{(-3)}}{M} \right)^{0.938} & Re \leq 1272 \\ 0.031 \cdot \left(\frac{t \cdot |F| \cdot 10^{(-3)}}{M} \right)^{1.124} & Re > 1272 \end{cases}$$

Figure. Variation of the penetration height with time under different operation conditions for a negative buoyancy jet

Figure. Development of the energy distribution ratio under different conditions.
(Each circle represents the energy distribution ratio of the layer at different times)

$$\eta_j = \frac{\sum_0^t C_{p,jm} m_{jm,t} (T_{jm,t} - T_{jm,0})}{\int_0^t m C_p (T_{in} - T_{out}) dt}$$

$$\eta_{32} = a \cdot \left(\frac{(t-t_{start}) \cdot |F| \cdot 10^{-3}}{M} \right)^b$$

$$\eta_2 = a \cdot \left(\frac{t \cdot |F| \cdot 10^{-3}}{M} \right)^b$$

First year of operation

- The range of soil temperature influenced by the water temperature continues to expand during the first year of operation.

Fourth year of operation

- By the fourth year of operation, the expansion trend of the soil temperature range influenced by the water temperature is not significant.

Convective heat transfer coefficient along sidewall

Start with an established soil temperature distribution

- The convective heat transfer coefficient along the side walls is around $25 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$
- For height with large temperature gradient, the convective heat transfer coefficient is getting smaller to around $15 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$

- Water temperature
- Soil temperature
- Water temperature < soil temperature
- Water temperature > soil temperature
- Convective heat transfer coefficient

Convective heat transfer coefficient of top surface

- The convective heat transfer coefficient of top surface is between 24 to 26 $W/m^2 \cdot K$
- The Nusselt number along the top surface can be fitted into correlations relating Grashof number

$$Nu_t = a \cdot (Ra_t)^b \quad (c \leq Gr \leq d)$$

Convective heat transfer coefficient of bottom surface

- The convective heat transfer coefficient of bottom surface is between 24 to 26 W/m²·K

- The Nusselt number along the bottom surface can be fitted into correlations relating Grashof number

$$Nu_b = a \cdot (Ra_b)^b$$

$$(c \leq Gr \leq d)$$

Alternative stratification arrangement

- Large horizontal pipe in order to provide low magnitude horizontal flow
- A hole of 0.3 m diameter in the bottom is acting as outlet
- $d=2$ m initially, in order to secure inlet velocities smaller than 3 cm/s
- For the charging case an increased inlet diameter of $d=4$ m was also tested

Alternative stratification arrangement

- Back flow and mixing in the large inlet pipe
- As a result the provided temperature drops due to mixing
- The developed velocities are much higher than expected
- This could be faced by a pierced disc in the front exit of the pipe or by a thinner pipe with a large nozzle at its end
- It was assumed that the backflow was solved before proceeding to further investigations

T profile at inlet

u profile, front view

T profile real/UDF

u profile real/UDF

Alternative simulating discharging

- The large pipe removes water from lower temperature layers
- The bottom inlet jet disturbs stratification
- The design was proven unsuitable for discharging
- Suggestions:
 - Horizontal discs to secure stratification in the bottom inlet are needed
 - Simpler pipes on top to facilitate outlet at the correct temperature level

Top large pipe outlet

Bottom inlet stream

- The energy balance results are really close to the real design in both cases
- Thermal stratification is preserved everywhere
- Smoother distribution of the hot inlet stream
- Similar velocity magnitude as the real for the d=2 m design (max 10 cm/s), lower for the d=4 m

T profile, d=2 m

u profile, d=2 m

T profile, d=4 m

u profile, d=4 m

Strengths

- Lower developed velocities
- Preserves thermal stratification
- Simpler and cheaper to construct
- Possibly a more cost effective component

Limitations

- Backflow still to be confronted
- Need some modifications before used for discharging
- Complex waterproof sealing to the HDPE liner on the sides (as for the real design)

- Lid is responsible for most of the heat losses
- More than 50% of the ground losses take place near the surface; insulation on the higher ground could be proven cost effective
- CFD calculations indicate higher losses from the lid
- Mixing due to inlet jet flow
- Different convective heat transfer coefficients for top, side and bottom surface
- Suggestion of an alternative stratification arrangement is not effective

Future research is necessary

System simulation models of TES

Why Trnsys?

- Why not CFD: time/effort-consuming, short-period analysis
- Trnsys – particularly applicable for system simulations
- It offers a simplified method: the water pit region with a 1 D model and surrounding soil region with a 2 D axisymmetric or a 3 D model

Simulation model of a hot water tank

Relative height, z

$z = \text{height} / \text{tank height}$

Tank heat loss, $(UA)_{s,a}$

$dz_1 = -1 \rightarrow (UA)_{s,a1}$ for whole store

$dz_1 > 0$

$(UA)_{s,\text{bot}}$

$(UA)_{s,\text{top}}$

$(UA)_{s,a1} - (UA)_{s,a4}$

Simulation model of a hot water tank

- Temperatures are calculated by solving a set of differential equations (energy balance)
- Array of $N_{\max} \times 3$
- $j = 2$: Data of tank
- $j = 1$: Data of hx1 and hx4
- $j = 3$: Data of hx2 and hx3
- 4 immersed heat exchangers (hx1, hx2, hx3, hx4)
- 10 double ports (dp1, dp2, ..., dp10)
- 1 electrical heating element

Energy balance of a tank node (j = 2)

The energy balance for each node (i) of the store (j=2) is represented by equation 4.1 using the logical switches ξ_i :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{V_s \cdot \rho_s \cdot c_{p,s}}{N_{\max}} \cdot \frac{\partial \vartheta_{i,2}}{\partial t} = & \sum_{p=1}^{10} \dot{m}_{dp} \cdot c_{p,s} \cdot [\xi_1 \cdot (\vartheta_{i-1,2} - \vartheta_{i,2}) + \xi_2 \cdot (\vartheta_{i,2} - \vartheta_{i+1,2})] \\ & + \xi_3 \cdot \frac{(UA)_{h1/4,s}^*}{nh1/4} \cdot (\vartheta_{i,1} - \vartheta_{i,2}) + \xi_4 \cdot \frac{(UA)_{h2/3,s}^*}{nh2/3} \cdot (\vartheta_{i,3} - \vartheta_{i,2}) \\ & + \lambda_{con} \cdot \frac{A_q}{H_s} \cdot N_{\max} \cdot [(\vartheta_{i+1,2} - \vartheta_{i,2}) + (\vartheta_{i-1,2} - \vartheta_{i,2})] \\ & - \frac{(UA)_{s,ak}}{ndzk} \cdot (\vartheta_{i,2} - \vartheta_{amb}) \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

Heat loss to ambient

with: $(UA)_{h1/4,s}^*$ = heat transfer capacity rate between the heat exchanger 1 and heat exchanger 4 and the store [kJ/(h K)]

$nh1/4$ = number of nodes occupied by heat exchanger 1 and 4 [-]

$(UA)_{h2/3,s}^*$ = heat transfer capacity rate between the hx 2/3 and the store [kJ/(h K)]

$nh2/4$ = number of nodes occupied by heat exchanger 2 and 3 [-]

$\xi_1 = 1$ if $\dot{m}_{dp} > 0$, else $\xi_1 = 0$

$\xi_2 = 1$ if $\dot{m}_{dp} < 0$, else $\xi_2 = 0$

$\xi_3 = 1$ if the store node i is in contact with the node i of heat exchanger 1 or 4, else $\xi_3 = 0$

$\xi_4 = 1$ if the store node i is in contact with the node i of heat exchanger 2 or 3, else $\xi_4 = 0$

λ_{con} effective thermal conductivity in the store [kJ/(m h K)]

- **Seasonal thermal energy storage (STES):**

(a) Reversed pyramid stump

(b) Reversed truncated cone

- **PTES:** quick charging/discharging ; short/long storage period; high energy density
- **Two main geometries of PTES:** Reversed pyramid stump, Reversed truncated cone

Available PTES models in Trnsys

PTES model	Water region	Soil region	Water/soil coupling for the side of the PTES
Type 342	1 D	2D axisymmetric	Zig zag
Type 343	1 D	2D axisymmetric	Straight line
Type 1300/1301	1 D	2D axisymmetric	Unknown
UGSTS	1 D	2D axisymmetric	Straight line
Type 1322	1 D	3D	Unknown

Model build-up for type 343

- Gravel water heat storage model (ICEPIT) from Trnssolar
- Modified by Kassel University enabling multi direct inlet/outlet port
- Similar as the UGSTS model but different mesh scheme

To reduce the numerical diffusion of multi-node model

-- increasing the number of nodes, calculation time rises

- **Input data :**
Charging temperature; Charging flowrate; Discharging flowrate; Ambient temperature; solar irradiance.
- **Charge/discharge determination:** Energy balance criteria
MATLAB applied to do data analysis work
- **Charge/discharge node (3 openings):** bottom, middle, top
- **Time step:** 10 min

Type No.	Top Opening	Middle Opening	Bottom Opening
1	+	-	-
2	-	+	-
3	-	-	+
4	+	-	+
5	+	+	-
6	-	+	+
7	Not working	Not working	Not working

Validation by the Dronninglund Heating Plant

- In operation since May 2014
- Solar fraction: approx. 40%, renewable energy fraction: 70%
- Includes: solar collector field, PTES (60,000 m³ storage volume), boilers, heat pump

- **PTES region:**

32 temperature sensors equally spaced from the top to the bottom of the PTES

- **Soil region:**

4 temperature sensors with a depth of 10 m, 15 m, 20 m and 25 m below the water level.

Location: 0.5 m from the edge.

Boundary conditions in the simulations

Ambient air temperatures

Inlet temperatures

Inlet flow rates

Experimental measurement data

Experimental vers. Trnsys

TRNSYS simulated data

Average PTES temperature

Temperature of the top opening

Temperature of the middle opening

Temperature of the bottom opening

Average temperature in storage

Heat loss predicted by the UGSTS model

Heat loss of the PTES in 2015	Unit	Measured	Simulated UGSTS	Simulated Type 343
Deviation with measurement	-	-	-19%	-8%
Total heat loss	MWh	1275	1030	1174
Top heat loss	MWh	-	667	775
Side heat loss	MWh	-	321	373
Bottom heat loss	MWh	-	41	25

PTES heat loss distribution

UGSTS model

Top	65%
Side	31%
Bottom	4%

Type 343

Top	66%
Side	32%
Bottom	2%

Soil temperatures

UGSTS model

Type 343

Comparison of soil and PTES temperatures

March 3, 2015

December 30, 2015

UGSTS model

Type 343

Temperatures in the PTES and the soil in a year

Development of temperatures in the PTES and the soil in a year

- **Storage efficiency:**

$$eff = \frac{\Delta E + E_{DC}}{E_{CH}}$$

- **Utilization frequency:**

$$N_{cyc} = \frac{E_{DC}}{E_{cyc,max}}$$

KPI for PTES in 2015	Unit	Measured	Simulated UGSTS	Simulated Type 343
Charged energy	MWh	12787	13718	12292
Deviation with measurement	%	-	7	4
Discharged energy	MWh	11957	12540	11730
Deviation with measurement	%	-	5	2
storage efficiency	%	90	89	90
No. of storage cycles	-	2.2	2.4	2.4
maximum temperature	°C	89	89	89
minimum temperature	°C	10	12	12

Conclusions

- Investigations show that
 - Both UGSTS and type 343 underestimate heat loss from the PTES, respectively by 19% and 8%.
 - UGSTS overestimates charged and discharged energy by 7% and 5%
 - Type 343 overestimated charged and discharged energy by 4% and 2%
- Future work
 - Better result could be achieved by refined inputs
 - Investigation of numerical diffusion
 - 3D modeling of soil around the PTES
 - Modeling of irregular shape of PTES
 - Inclusion of underground water/water flow in soil region

A review of the 4 lectures on TES

Hot water tank
Water pit heat storage

Phase change material
heat storage

Steel tank

Water pit (PTES)

Borehole storage (BTES)

Aquifer storage

A good example of Danish district energy system for heating and electricity production

Standby heat loss and cooling of TES

$$T_{end} = T_a^* + (T_{start} - T_a^*) \exp\left(\frac{-t_{end}(UA_{top} + UA_{soil})}{mC_p}\right)$$

pyramid

Volume under ground level = truncated pyramid

$$\begin{aligned} V_{\text{underground}} &= \frac{h}{3} (\text{Area 2} + \text{Area 1} + \sqrt{\text{Area 2} * \text{Area 1}}) \\ &= \frac{h}{3} (a^2 + b^2 + a \cdot b) \end{aligned}$$

Heat loss from the PTES

Heat loss coefficient from the side and the bottom:

$$Q_{side} = A_{side} U_{side} (T_{ptes} - T_{soil}) \qquad U_{side} = \frac{1}{\sum R_{side}} = \frac{k_{soil}}{t_{side}}$$

Heat loss coefficient from the cover:

$$Q_{top} = A_{top} U_{top} (T_{ptes} - T_a) \qquad U_{top} = \frac{1}{\sum R_{top}} = \frac{1}{\frac{t_{top}}{k_{insu}} + \frac{1}{h_e}}$$

$$h_e = h_{convection} + h_{radiation}$$

$$h_{convection} = 5.8 \frac{W}{m^2 K} \qquad \text{Wind} = 1 \text{ m/s}$$

$$h_{convection} = 8.8 \frac{W}{m^2 K} \qquad \text{Wind} = 2 \text{ m/s}$$

$$h_{radiation} = \frac{\varepsilon_{cover} \cdot \sigma \cdot (T_{cover} + T_{sky}) \cdot (T_{cover}^2 + T_{sky}^2) \cdot (T_{cover} - T_{sky})}{(T_{cover} - T_a)}$$

Iteration is needed to determine Q_{top}

Heat loss coefficients of hot water tank, U_{st}

$$U_{\text{tank top}} = \frac{\frac{\pi}{4} (d_y + e_s)^2}{\frac{e_t}{\lambda} + \frac{1}{\alpha_{\text{top}}}} \quad \text{W/K}$$

$$U_{\text{tank side}} = \frac{\pi}{\frac{1}{2\lambda} \ln \frac{d_y + 2e_s}{d_y} + \frac{1}{\alpha_{\text{side}}} \frac{1}{d_y + 2e_s}} H \quad \text{W/K}$$

$$U_{\text{tank bottom}} = \frac{\frac{\pi}{4} (d_y + e_s)^2}{\frac{e_b}{\lambda} + \frac{1}{\alpha_{\text{bot}}}} \quad \text{W/K}$$

d_y : outer diameter of the tank.
 H : height of the tank.
 α_{top} , α_{bot} , α_{side} : heat transfer coefficient of the top (10 W/m²K), the bottom 5.88 W/m²K and the side surface of the tank (7.69 W/m²K) respectively.

Insulation, thermal conductivity λ
 Insulation thickness e_t , e_s , e_b

Thermal stratification in hot water tank/PTES

Cause:

- Water density is temperature dependent
- Higher water temperature → Lower density → Upper part of the TES
- Lower water temperature → Higher density → Lower part of the TES

Benefit:

- Higher temperature in upper part of TES → lower auxiliary energy consumption
- Lower temperature in lower part of TES → Higher renewable energy efficiency
- Overall, higher system efficiency

How to maintain thermal stratification in TES:

- Correct Inlet/outlet placement: cold water inlet/outlet at the bottom
- Diffuser designs to minimize mixing due to water inlet

Better thermal stratification in the TES means:

- Higher charge/discharge efficiency
- Higher Richardson number for inlet
- Lower Froude number for inlet
- Lower MIX number
- Higher exergy efficiency

Key performance indicator: MIX number

District heating companies:

- 1. Secure stable supply of heat (hourly demand fully covered by DH)
- 2. Decrease heating cost for the consumers by choosing the cheapest heating source

The variable cost of heat production depends on electricity prices

No subsidies/incentives

corporate tax rate, asset depreciation, the discount rate are not considered

The residual value of the system after the life time is zero.

Lift time of the system is 20 years

$$LCOH = \frac{I_0 + 20C_t}{20E_t} = \frac{\frac{I_0}{20} + C_t}{E_t}$$

If there is a bank loan for the capital investment, the annual interest rate (*itr*) could be considered

$$LCOH = \frac{itr * I_0 + 20C_t}{20E_t} = \frac{\frac{itr * I_0}{20} + C_t}{E_t}$$

The annual payment of the loan ($itr * I_0 / 20$) consists of:

1. Principal payment: pay off the investment cost of the system, I_0
2. Interest payment

Thanks for your attention!